

31st International Symposium on Lepton Photon Interactions at High Energies

Recent Belle II results on time-dependent CP violation and charm

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On behalf of the Belle II collaboration

17-21 July 2023

Abstract

Analysis of time-dependent CP violation are flagship measurements of the Belle II physics program. We present new results on the effective value of the CKM angle $\sin 2\phi_1$ in $b \rightarrow q\bar{q}s$ transitions using the dataset collected between 2019–2022. These modes are sensitive probes of physics beyond the Standard Model (SM). In addition, we discuss world-leading determinations of charm-hadron lifetimes and the development of a novel charm-flavor tagger.

1 Introduction

Measurements of time-dependent CP -violation in $b \rightarrow q\bar{q}s$ transitions are powerful probes to indirectly search for generic new physics. They proceed through loop-suppressed decays that are potentially affected by non-Standard Model (SM) amplitudes and benefit from a clean theory prediction [1]. Therefore, they can be tested against the SM value measured in tree-level $b \rightarrow c\bar{c}s$ transitions. This class of decays, which includes $B^0 \rightarrow \phi K_S^0$, $B^0 \rightarrow K_S^0 \pi^0$ and $B^0 \rightarrow K_S^0 K_S^0 K_S^0$, often feature neutral particles in the final states, which are challenging to reconstruct. In addition, the small branching fractions make the currently available datasets statistically limited with respect to the theory prediction. Belle II is in the unique position to improve the current experimental knowledge due to its capabilities with neutral particle reconstruction and increasing dataset.

Measurements of charm-hadron lifetimes constitute an important test of non-perturbative QCD (such as the lifetime hierarchy). Detectors at e^+e^- colliders, are the ideal place to probe absolute lifetimes thanks to their decay-time independent selection efficiency. Belle II has performed world-leading and independent determinations of the lifetime of several charm-hadron species (D^0 , D^+ , D_s^+ , Λ_c^+ and Ω_c^0). The size of the available dataset used for CP violation measurements in charm has been effectively doubled by the development of a new algorithm to determine the flavor of neutral D^0 meson.

Belle II is a high-energy physics experiment operating at the SuperKEKB collider. The detector has collected 362 fb^{-1} of data at the $\Upsilon(4S)$ resonance, corresponding to 387×10^6 $B\bar{B}$ pairs, and 42.3 fb^{-1} off-resonance. The detector is designed to reconstruct the decays of heavy-flavor mesons and τ leptons in energy-asymmetric e^+e^- collisions. With respect to its predecessor, the detector has achieved twice as good impact parameter resolution (10 and 15 μm in the radial and longitudinal direction, respectively) thanks to the new pixel detector, which is placed closer to the interaction region. The measurements of absolute lifetimes, determined from the distance between the interaction point and decay vertex, rely on the constant calibration of the position of the e^+e^- interaction region.

2 Measurements of charm-hadron lifetimes and charm-flavor tagger

Belle II has performed the single most precise determination of the Λ_c^+ [2] lifetime and provided an independent measurement of the Ω_c^0 lifetime [3], confirming the lifetime hierarchy observed by LHCb [4, 5]. The distributions of the proper-decay times, from which the lifetimes are determined, are displayed in Fig. 1. The simultaneous fit of the signal and sideband regions, displayed in the top and bottom panels, allow for a simulation-free modeling of the signal and background component.

The most precise determination of the D_s^+ lifetime has been performed using half of the available Belle II dataset [6]. The invariant mass distribution of events reconstructed as $D_s^+ \rightarrow \phi\pi^+$ and lifetime fit to the events in the signal region are shown in Fig. 2. The contribution of secondary D_s^+ from B decays, which would bias the determination of the lifetime, is efficiently rejected with a minimum requirement on the D_s^+ momentum. Similarly to other charm-hadron lifetime measurements, the leading systematic uncertainties come from the modeling of the t resolution, background distribution and imperfect detector alignment. The measured values of the lifetimes are reported in Tab 1 together with the current world averages [7].

The flavor of neutral D^0 mesons is traditionally determined by reconstructing

Figure 1: Distribution of the proper-decay time in $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow pK^+\pi^-$ (left) and $\Omega_c^0 \rightarrow \Omega^-\pi^+$ (right) decays [2, 3].

Figure 2: Invariant mass (left) and distribution of the proper-decay time (right) in $D_s^+ \rightarrow \phi\pi^+$ decays [6].

Table 1: Comparison of recent Belle II results (where the first uncertainties are statistical, while the second are systematic) and world average values of the charm-hadron lifetimes.

Observable	Belle II (207 fb^{-1}) [fs]	World Average [fs]
$\tau(\Lambda_c^+)$	$203.20 \pm 0.89 \pm 0.77$	201.5 ± 2.7
$\tau(\Omega_c^0)$	$243 \pm 48 \pm 11$	274.5 ± 12.4
$\tau(D_s^+)$	$498.7 \pm 1.7^{+1.1}_{-0.8}$	504 ± 4

the $D^{*+} \rightarrow D^0\pi^+$ decay chain. However, D^0 mesons produced directly in charm pair production are not tagged by this method. By exploiting charge correlations between the D^0 flavor and tracks in the rest of the event, it is possible to recover the flavor for these events. Belle II has achieved an effective tagging efficiency of $(49.91 \pm 0.07 \pm 0.51)\%$ in data calibrated with flavor-specific decays, where the first uncertainty is statistical and the second is systematic [8].

3 Measurements of $\sin 2\phi_1$ in $b \rightarrow q\bar{q}s$ transitions

Pairs of neutral B^0 mesons are produced in a quantum-entangled state from the decay of an $\Upsilon(4S)$ resonance. The proper-time difference Δt is estimated using the decay vertex positions of the two B^0 mesons in the event along the boost axis. The knowledge of decay times is enhanced by the constraint from the beam spot profile in combination with the new nano-beam scheme, achieving a Δt resolution of less than 1 ps. The Δt distribution for B^0 decays to CP eigenstates is:

$$\mathcal{P}(\Delta t, q) = \frac{e^{-|\Delta t|/\tau_{B^0}}}{4\tau_{B^0}} \left\{ 1 + q[S \sin(\Delta m_d \Delta t) - C \cos(\Delta m_d \Delta t)] \right\}, \quad (1)$$

where q is the flavor of the other B^0 in the event ($q = +1$ for B^0 and $q = -1$ for \bar{B}^0), and C and S are the direct and mixing induced CP asymmetries. In $b \rightarrow q\bar{q}s$ transitions, the value of S could differ from the value of $\sin 2\phi_1$ measured in $b \rightarrow c\bar{c}s$ transitions, due to the contribution from non-SM amplitudes, while C is expected to be zero within the SM. The decays $B^0 \rightarrow \phi K_S^0$, $B^0 \rightarrow K_S^0 K_S^0 K_S^0$ and $B^0 \rightarrow K_S^0 \pi^0$ all proceed through $b \rightarrow q\bar{q}s$ gluonic penguin transitions and therefore provide inputs to the effective value of $\sin 2\phi_1$.

The $B^0 \rightarrow \phi K_S^0$ decay vertex is well determined with two prompt tracks from the $\phi \rightarrow K^+ K^-$ decay. It receives a contribution from non-resonant $B^0 \rightarrow K^+ K^- K_S^0$ decays with the same final state but opposite CP eigenvalue, which dilute the observable CP asymmetries. In order to disentangle the non-resonant background component, we perform a multidimensional fit including the cosine of the helicity angle, in which the $B^0 \rightarrow \phi K_S^0$ and $B^0 \rightarrow K^+ K^- K_S^0$ have different distributions. The $B^0 \rightarrow K_S^0 K_S^0 K_S^0$ decay proceeds through the same underlying quark transition as $B^0 \rightarrow \phi K_S^0$. It has the advantage of not being affected from opposite- CP backgrounds. Since the K_S^0 decay on average outside of the pixel detector, it is experimentally challenging to reconstruct due to the absence of prompt tracks to form a vertex. The decay vertex reconstruction relies on the K_S^0 trajectory and profile of the interaction point. The $B^0 \rightarrow K_S^0 \pi^0$ decay has a higher effective branching fraction than $B^0 \rightarrow \phi K_S^0$ and $B^0 \rightarrow K_S^0 K_S^0 K_S^0$ but slightly larger theoretical uncertainties [1]. The value of C measured in $B^0 \rightarrow K_S^0 \pi^0$ is also limiting the precision of the isospin sum-rule in $B \rightarrow hh$ decays. The signal reconstruction requires excellent performance with neutrals, due to the absence of prompt tracks and presence of a π^0 in the final state. In total, we reconstruct 162 ± 17 $B^0 \rightarrow \phi K_S^0$, 158_{-13}^{+14} $B^0 \rightarrow K_S^0 K_S^0 K_S^0$ and 415_{-25}^{+26} $B^0 \rightarrow K_S^0 \pi^0$ events using a sample of 362 fb^{-1} [9, 10]. The fit to the Δt distributions and corresponding CP asymmetries are displayed in Fig. 3. The measured values of the CP asymmetries are reported, together with the current world averages, in Tab 2.

Figure 3: Projections of the Δt fit and CP asymmetries in $b \rightarrow q\bar{q}s$ decays: $B^0 \rightarrow \phi K_S^0$ (top left), $B^0 \rightarrow K_S^0\pi^0$ (top right) and $B^0 \rightarrow K_S^0K_S^0K_S^0$ (bottom) [9, 10].

Table 2: Comparison of recent Belle II results (where the first uncertainties are statistical, while the second are systematic) and world average of CP asymmetries in $b \rightarrow q\bar{q}s$ transitions.

Observable		Belle II (362 fb^{-1})	World Average
$B^0 \rightarrow \phi K_S^0$	C	$-0.31 \pm 0.20 \pm 0.05$	0.01 ± 0.14
	S	$0.54 \pm 0.26^{+0.06}_{-0.08}$	$0.74^{+0.11}_{-0.13}$
$B^0 \rightarrow K_S^0K_S^0K_S^0$	C	$-0.07^{+0.20}_{-0.15} \pm 0.02$	-0.15 ± 0.12
	S	$-1.37^{+0.35}_{-0.45} \pm 0.03$	-0.83 ± 0.17
$B^0 \rightarrow K_S^0\pi^0$	C	$-0.04^{+0.14}_{-0.15} \pm 0.05$	0.01 ± 0.10
	S	$0.75^{+0.20}_{-0.23} \pm 0.04$	0.57 ± 0.17

4 Summary

Belle II has performed world-leading measurements of the charm-hadron lifetimes and provided independent determination of the charm-baryon lifetime hierarchy. The reach of CP violation measurements has been enhanced by the development of a novel charm-flavor tagger, recovering the tagging information on part of the data which would be discarded by traditional approaches. Measurements of time-dependent CP violation in $b \rightarrow q\bar{q}s$ transitions are essential to probe generic non-SM physics in loops. Many of these modes are exclusive to Belle II, due to its unique neutral reconstruction capabilities. Recent determinations of CP asymmetries in $B^0 \rightarrow \phi K_S^0$, $B^0 \rightarrow K_S^0 K_S^0 K_S^0$ and $B^0 \rightarrow K_S^0 \pi^0$ have been reported using the full Belle II dataset.

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